

Assessing the accuracy of Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer (VIIRS) and MultiUltra-high Resolution (MUR) Sea-Surface Temperature products for inclusion of a model to forecast blooms of *Alexandrium catenella* in south-central Alaska

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Abstract

The toxic harmful algal bloom species *Alexandrium catenella* has been observed to bloom in Alaskan coastal waters when sea surface temperatures (SST) exceed approximately 8°C. Consequently, acquiring, fine scale SST data for Alaskan coastal waters represents a critical first step in developing ecological models capable of predicting the occurrence of toxic *Alexandrium* blooms in this region. Remotely sensed satellite SST records represent the most comprehensive SST data set, but before those data can be used, the satellite data require validation which was the goal of this study. Specifically, we compare a remotely sensed monthly sea surface climatological data set produced by NASA's Jet Propulsion Laboratory with seven meteorological buoys provided by the National Ocean and Atmosphere Administration (NOAA) National Data Buoy Center (NDBC). The comparisons were done on a point-to-pixel basis as well as an aerial estimation method. The selected study area, the Kodiak Archipelago in Alaska (U.S.A.), is characterized as possessing a varied coastline, filled with a number of coves and embayments. Three of the NDBC buoys are located in embayments and an additional one is in the ~40 km wide Shelikof Strait, with the remaining three offshore. The remotely sensed and in situ measurements were highly correlated providing the basis for the extraction fine scale SST data for the Alaska region over the past 10+ years which can be subsequently incorporated into bloom prediction models.

Keywords: water temperature, sea surface temperature, Alaska, *Alexandrium catenella*, forecasting

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Introduction

Sea-Surface Temperature (SST) is one of the most easily quantifiable environmental parameters in the marine environment, and one of the most used in biophysical modeling exercises. Many biological properties are influenced by SST, including phytoplankton growth rates and nutrient uptake kinetics (Lomas and Glibert, 1999). Work by Vandersea *et al.* (2017) found temperature was the factor best predicting when toxic *Alexandrium catenella* blooms occur in Alaskan coastal waters. If accurate models predicting the likelihood of *Alexandrium* blooms are to be developed, it is imperative to have reliable and detailed estimates of SST for this region. Synoptic remote sensing represents the most robust way to quantify this parameter. Consequently, an intensive validation for satellite sensed Alaskan sea surface temperatures was undertaken as the first key step in developing predictive models for *A. catenella* bloom occurrence.

Fig. 1. Locations of the NDBC buoys used in this manuscript. The polygon shown is what was used to extract the data from the MUR imagery for the comparison shown in figure 3.

Material and Methods

Water Temperature Data

The water temperature (WTMP) data were acquired from the National Data Buoy Center (NDBC, 2021). These data are collected as frequently as every quarter of an hour. Daily and monthly means were calculated with missing data values discarded. Seven stations were considered that are in the vicinity of the Kodiak Archipelago (Fig. 1).

Sea Surface Temperature Data

Monthly SST data were acquired from NOAA PolarWatch (2021), from NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) Multi-scale Ultra-high Resolution (MUR) SST product. This is a global product combining an array of data, including microwave data, and mapped to a 0.01° spatial resolution (JPL, 2021). It should be noted that part of the data stream into the MUR modelled SST product was from the NDBC buoys (Chin *et al.*, 2017). Daily Sea Surface Temperature (SST) was acquired from the NOAA Coastwatch program from the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer (VIIRS) at a spatial resolution of 750 m (Coastwatch, 2021).

Comparison Methods

The MUR monthly data were compared to the NDBC water temperatures in two ways. The first was a traditional point-to-pixel matchup. A 3 x 3 box of pixels was extracted from each monthly image and the median of this 3 x 3 box was calculated and compared directly with the monthly median water temperature from the NDBC data.

The second method was adopted by Wynne *et al.* (2021) where a polygon was drawn around the seven buoys in figure 1 and then all of the

included data were extracted and averaged. This polygon is shown in figure 1. In this manner, each month had a single point. This average was compared to the mean of the seven different NDBC stations. This process was termed the integrated method by Wynne *et al.* (2021).

The mean daily water temperature was calculated from the NDBC data. A 3 x 3 box around the point of interest was extracted from the daily VIIRS SST. The median was calculated from the extracted points. A daily matchup was achieved if a single point from the 3 x 3 matchup was available.

Results and Discussion

A least squares regression from the point-to-pixel match-ups was used to assess differences in monthly MUR data (Fig. 2). The regression line fit well, indicating relatively low error and bias.

Fig. 2. Regression between the monthly NDBC water temperatures and the combined monthly MUR SST for the stations in figure 1 based on a point-to-pixel matchup technique and the monthly MUR data water temperatures.

Fig. 3. Relationship between the monthly NDBC water temperature and the monthly MUR SST from the integrated technique (orange line). Each month is reduced to a single point.

Using this method, the monthly mean NDBC water temperature data and the monthly MUR SST data were also compared using a least-squares regression analysis for the integrated technique (Fig. 3).

The daily water temperature and from the NDBC and the daily VIIRS regression is shown in figure 4.

The slopes from the monthly point-to-pixel matchup (Fig. 2) and the monthly integrated matchup (Fig. 3) vary by less than 2%. This indicates that the integrated method produces a reliable representation of water temperatures around the Kodiak Archipelago. This could have important ramifications for subsequent HAB forecasting work in that datasets with a course spatial resolution may be sufficient for forecasting across southern Alaska.

Fig. 4. Correlation between the daily NDBC water temperature and the daily VIIRS SST for the stations in figure 1 based on a point-to-pixel matchup technique.

The slopes between the regression lines of the VIIRS daily imagery and the MUR monthly imagery using the point-to-pixel matchup are also within good agreement varying by ~3%.

It appears that the two different SST products both underestimate the water temperatures by approximately 10%. This bias can be corrected relatively easily, by dividing the SST by the slope of the regression line. The results here indicate that the VIIRS daily product, with high spatial resolution (750 m pixel vs 1 km for MUR) shows good agreement with field water temperatures around the Kodiak Archipelago. Similarly, the MUR monthly SST product shows good agreement with NDBC water temperature, and with the high spatial resolution VIIRS data. The results of this analysis indicate ability to provide gap filled coverage would be a good choice for a monthly SST product in the Gulf of Alaska for any potential biophysical model to predict the occurrence of *Alexandrium* blooms.

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References

Chin, T.M., Vazquez-Cuervo, J., Armstrong, E.M. (2017). *Remote Sens. of Environ.* 200, 154-169.

Coastwatch (2021). [//coastwatch.noaa.gov/cw/satellite-data-products/sea-surface-temperature/noaa-coastwatch-cogridded.html](https://coastwatch.noaa.gov/cw/satellite-data-products/sea-surface-temperature/noaa-coastwatch-cogridded.html). Accessed November 11th, 2021.

Lomas, M.W. and Gilbert, P.M. (1999). *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 44, 556-572.

NDBC, National Data Buoy Center (2021). [//www.ndbc.noaa.gov](https://www.ndbc.noaa.gov). Accessed September 9th, 2021.

Vandersea, M.W., Kibler, S.R., Van Sant, S.B., Tester, P.A., *et al.*, (2017). *Phycol.* 58, 303-320.

Wynne, T.T., Mishra, S., Meredith, A., Litaker, R.W., Stumpf, R.P. (2021). *Remote Sens.* 13, 2305.

